

Teacher Perspectives and Experiences on Distributed Leadership Practice in Schools to Enhance Learner Performance

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The purpose of this study was to investigate teacher perceptions of how distributed leadership practices are enacted in Goromonzi district schools. High academic performance can only be possible if all departments in schools are effective. The ever-changing times and the increasing workload for school heads in schools call for an all-embracing approach to school leadership if learners are to realise academic growth in schools. The study employed the qualitative research approach and a multiple case study research design. A sample of three high-performing schools made up of a government, private, and a council school were purposively selected. Three teachers were purposively selected from the three schools, one from each school. Structured interviews, observations, and document analysis were used to gather data. The study findings indicate that principals enacting distributed instructional leadership practices can heighten school academic performance. This is characterised by teachers partaking in varied leadership practices, such as visioning schools and shared instructional supervisory practice. The study recommends the nurturing of teachers through the distributed leadership practice for improved school performance.

Keywords: Zimbabwe, school leadership, instructional leadership, distributed leadership, leadership practices

The crucial nature of education in societies has made communities place great expectations on school heads to improve learner academic performance. This calls for improved school leadership practices by school heads. Cabral et al. (2019) argue that school leadership is an important aspect that can improve the performance of schools. In acknowledging the importance of school leadership in the current education system, Kumari (2021) is of the view that distributed leadership is one of the most important leadership practices that can enhance the quality of teaching and learning because it involves many members in a school. In addition, since school heads cannot be everywhere in a school at any one given moment, this suggests the importance of distributed leadership. Given that leadership can be regarded as a shared social process emerging from the interactions of various people, it was of interest to find out how the distributed leadership practice was enacted in schools by school heads for improved school performance.

Distributed leadership advocates that leadership stretches across several participants (Bolden, 2011; Spillane, 2005). This is supported by Kumari (2021) who argues that leadership not only

involves the school head and the deputy head but all members of the school community. The traditional leadership model of a single heroic leader that practices a top-down leadership function has been replaced by distributed leadership (UÇAR, 2021). This is believed to respond well to the complexity of modern-day educational institutions that cannot be led by a single leader (Hallinger & Kovačević, 2021). As a contemporary leadership theory in education, leadership has the potential to bring about improvement in schools.

Spillane and Diamond (2007) believe that distributed leadership can be effectively used in managing schools and as a lens to examine leadership activities in schools. It acknowledges the contribution of all members of the organization towards school leadership, irrespective of whether it is formal or informal leadership. This suggests that leadership resides in both the principal and other members of the school. Spillane (2005) argues that the importance of leadership practice is how it is distributed in schools, a topic which has not been fully explored. There is, therefore, a need to determine how distributed leadership practices are enacted in high-performing schools that make them different from other schools. Consequently, this inspired us to conduct this study to determine how distributed leadership is enacted in high-performing schools that have a record of good academic results, with particular focus on Zimbabwean primary schools.

Primary schools in Zimbabwe have two departments, the Infant and Junior departments. A teacher in charge (TIC) leads the Infant Department with their appointment to this post made by the school head. The Junior Department runs from Grade 3 to Grade 7 (Curriculum framework for Primary & Secondary Education 2015, 2022). The main driver of instructional activities in primary schools is the school head, assisted by the deputy head and the teacher in charge (TIC). Shava et al. (2021) point out that there is a growing concern that schools are not performing well in Zimbabwe and the entire southern African region. They cite the lack of requisite

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knowledge and skills among school heads to lead their schools towards sustaining high-quality learning outcomes. It is therefore important that school heads capitalize on the skills and expertise that reside in teachers for the benefit of learners (Göksoy, 2015) thus highlighting the need for distributed leadership in schools.

Effective leadership of instructional activities is crucial in education. Instructional leadership encompasses varied practices and processes that make schools develop (Bush, 2013; Mestry & Pillay, 2013). Grenda and Hackmann (2014) argue that school heads are overwhelmed by competing duties, which include management tasks, monitoring of instructional activities, financial supervision, learner issues, and accountability to raise student academic achievement. Thus, having the principal as the single person with all the expertise to lead all these activities to stardom cannot be sustained (Göksoy, 2015; Spillane, 2005). Therefore, distributed leadership, which can help improve instructional activities at school must be enacted in schools for high academic results. In fact, leaders influence and are also influenced by followers (Grenda & Hackman, 2014). This reciprocal influence exists in the sense that school heads direct schools and the efforts of members towards the vision of the school, whereas teachers also influence leaders through their expertise and experiences as people who work directly with learners, possessing more knowledge about learners than any other person. This therefore points to the need for the enactment of the distributed leadership practice in schools.

Although distributed leadership is regarded as an important model of education management, Shava et al. (2021) argue that an understanding of its practices in education leadership discourse is still broad and contested. A review of literature on leadership reveals several challenges when attempting to explain distributed leadership. A lack of clarity and consistency in the definition of distributed leadership exists and some researchers regard the absence of a clear definition as a limitation, although this has not hindered any empirical investigations on the practical application of distributed leadership. Shabalala, Hebe, and Mnguni (2023) views distributed leadership as an approach that encourages shared leadership between a leader and followers in an organization. This, therefore, indicates that distributed leadership must be shared among different stakeholders.

Statement of the Problem

Despite increasing interest in distributed leadership to improve school effectiveness and learner performance, there remains a limited understanding of how teachers perceive and experience this leadership model in practice. Many schools continue to operate under traditional hierarchical leadership structures, potentially limiting the benefits of shared leadership. The lack of insight into teachers' perspectives on distributed leadership hinders efforts to implement it effectively and sustainably. Without a deeper understanding of how teachers engage with, interpret, and contribute to distributed leadership practices, efforts to enhance learner performance through leadership reform may be undermined.

Research Question

The question guiding the research was: How is distributed leadership practice enacted in Zimbabwean primary schools?

Theoretical Framework

Several new and old theories on leadership have been used in

previous leadership studies (Bush & Ng, 2019; Göksoy, 2015). This study utilized the distributed leadership theory put forward by Spillane (2005). The choice of the theory was based on the premise that schools that enact distributed leadership have high learner academic results, and those without low academic results. This study, therefore, wanted to find out how distributed leadership practices were enacted in schools that had high academic performance. The theory discourages the idea of solo heroism by school heads in leading schools, thus informing this study on distributed leadership practices in high-performing primary schools. Teachers possess varied expertise, signifying that school heads are not the only individuals with expertise to transform schools into greatness.

Torres (2019) argues that schools that enact the distributed leadership practice have a culture of mutual responsibility and collaboration and increase the participation of teachers in their schools' decision-making activities (Kumari, 2021). Also, it has been found that the main purpose of distributed leadership is to create secondary level leaders within the school and thus give more opportunities for teachers to improve their leadership skills. Thus, school heads need to consciously support and facilitate leadership from other members of staff in the school through making good use of teachers' skills at appropriate times and levels.

In today's world, in complex systems such as schools, leadership does not take place through a single individual but through a set of collaborative practices among professionals in the school context. In distributed leadership, school heads interact with other staff members in the context of their school and on precise responsibilities (Spillane et al., 2004). Limitations exist when leadership is centered on one individual at the expense of vice school heads, TICs, and subject specialists, who are crucial in the school system. The theory came in as a relief to schools because of the challenging burden on school heads, who were expected to lead schools to great heights (Spillane, 2005).

Method

In this study, the qualitative research approach and the multiple case study design were used to examine how instructional leadership practices were enacted in high-performing primary schools. This was done through interviews, observations, and document analysis. The use of triangulation helped researchers to examine the integrity of data given by participants and to increase accuracy and credibility. We engaged teachers in schools and observed how they interacted in their work situations. Through the case study design, careful consideration of the main activities that characterize instructional leadership was made possible. We used the multiple case study design because it involves collecting data from various sites, which are the selected high-performing primary schools (Yin, 2014) and we believe that it is in such schools that distributed leadership takes place. The multiple case study design was used to achieve credible results (Merriam, 2009). We worked closely with teachers and listened to their responses during interviews to unpack their understanding of distributed leadership practices in their schools (Minichiello & Kottler, 2010). As qualitative research concentrates on direct experiences, we gained an understanding of the participants' perceptions of distributed leadership in the context of their schools.

Three high-performing primary schools were selected based on

recommendations from the district supervisor. We approached the District Education Office and requested information on high-performing schools as per their records of pass rates and supervision reports done in the previous three years. From the information provided by the District Office, we purposively sampled three primary schools that were well known for their leadership practices. Three teachers were also purposively sampled from the three schools (Creswell, 2009) with one teacher from each of the schools. The idea behind using purposive sampling was to have participants with information on the phenomena that was under research, that is distributed leadership. The respondents were selected based on their leadership prowess in different school activities, their length of stay at the schools and the academic performance of their learners, information that was got from school reports. These teachers were able to give significant data on distributed leadership. Creswell and Creswell (2018) argue that qualitative researchers sample participants help them answer their research questions. The participants provided thick descriptions and in-depth information about distributed leadership at their schools.

We explained in full the purpose of our research and did not hide our identities. We asked for their informed consent and had them complete informed consent forms. We also informed the participants of their anonymity and the confidentiality of the information that they gave us. We concealed the identities of the participants by using pseudonyms. We also made the participants aware that their participation was voluntary, and they could withdraw from the study anytime without any consequence. Having obtained permission from the Ministry, field visits were made. We adhered to the rules related to qualitative research.

Data Analysis

A thematic analysis of data that was gathered was done. All the data from interviews were transcribed and then the information was content analysed. Information gathered from observations and responses from participants was coded and then classified into different themes, which was to ease the interpretation of the interviews (Vaismoradi & Snelgrove, 2019). The researchers validated the analysis by comparing the audio recordings of the participants to the transcriptions that were done. This was to ensure credibility and trustworthiness. Participants were allowed to verify the correctness of the transcriptions that had been made by the researchers of their interviews and from the descriptions of observations that had been made in the schools, that is, member checking. Creswell and Creswell (2018) states that through member checking, research bias is eliminated and establishes whether the responses by the participants have been properly understood by the researcher.

Results

Case 1: The story of Mrs Rega

Mrs Rega, the TIC at Matanga Primary School, was just over 50 years old and held a Diploma in Education as her highest qualification at the time of study. She is quite an experienced teacher, having been in the teaching field for close to 30 years. She led the Infants Department, which comprised Early Childhood Development (ECD) A and B classes and grades 1 and 2. She was one of those teachers who had been at the school for a long time.

Due to her long tenure at the school, we believed that she was an

appropriate participant to know how visions and missions were created at the school. These are crucial elements of schools which show the direction of schools and how they want to reach their destinations (Allen et al., 2018). She understood most of the school processes. She explained how the school vision was created, since she participated in its formulation. This was indicated by her response when she said:

We sat down as staff and discussed the vision and mission statements. I remember that time, some years back, we would ask questions like, 'Why are we here or what is it that we want to do to our learners, to our community and to the country?' That is how we came up with the vision and mission statements.

Mrs Rega's quote somewhat corroborates the development process that took place in crafting a vision at Matanga Primary School. The participation of teachers in the development process comes through, thus suggesting distributed leadership. We discovered that teachers who were present when the school crafted its vision were indeed involved in crafting the school's vision and mission statements. This was noted when Mrs Rega said, *'We sat down as staff and discussed the vision and mission statements. I remember that time, some years back ...'*. The statement suggests a degree of teacher participation in this instructional leadership activity. When we analysed documents given to us by Mrs Rega, we discovered that teachers were organised into teams that came up with draft visions of the school. These were later combined and turned into a final vision document of the school by a smaller group that was composed of the school administrative team, which was led by the school head. This was evidence of staff member involvement in crafting the school vision at Matanga Primary School. Hallinger and Hosseingholizadeh (2019) advocated that school heads have a role to work with teachers in crafting goals that focus on learner academic performance. The goals derive from the vision of the school; thus, teachers need to understand the school vision so that they all work towards a common purpose.

Alhouti and Male (2017) pointed out that effective school heads supervise teaching and learning to improve learner outcomes. Supervision of instructional activities informs school heads of what takes place in classrooms and assists teachers to refine their competencies for effective instruction, leading to the achievement of school objectives (Heaton, 2016). The supervision of teachers was a shared activity at Matanga Primary School between the school principal, vice principal, and the TIC. This was confirmed by Mrs Rega, who said: *'These (lesson observations) are conducted by the school head, the deputy head, and the TIC.'* Mrs Rega's statement means that *teacher supervision at Matanga Primary School was done by the three supervisors. To ascertain Mrs Rega's statements, we analysed supervision crits in the school supervision file. The reports were done by different supervisors, for the infants department, supervision crits were done by Mrs Rega, for grades three to five, it was the deputy head and for grades six and seven, it was the school head. This leadership practice suggests distributed leadership.*

As a supervisor, Mrs Rega emphasized the importance of giving feedback to teachers after a lesson observation:

I usually give a few highlights of the teacher's performance just after the lesson, while we all still remember how the lesson would have progressed. ... As for the narrative report, it is usually after two to three days.

Mrs Rega's explanation clearly indicates her involvement in the practice of supervising teachers at work, indicating that instructional leadership activities were not meant for school heads only. Instead of supervising all the teachers at the school, the principal had the TIC to lead the Infants Department.

When it came to staff development at Matanga Primary School, Mrs Rega was very appreciative of the support offered by the school principal. This was noted in her explanation of the principal's support of staff-development programs:

Yes, she (the principal) does, especially being at a very big school. Recently, she (the principal) said: 'Don't wait for me for you to have your staff-development workshops; make sure you do your own things there. If I have time, I can come and see what you will be doing, but if I don't get the time, go on and staff develop each other so that you keep the school going.' We do a lot of staff development in reading. Teachers from within the department conduct staff development; we do not call people from outside, because we have a lot of people with the capacity to staff-develop others.

The principal authorized staff members to conduct staff-development programs in their departments without having to wait for her. Empowering the TIC to conduct staff development in the department indicated her acknowledgement of the capacity of other teachers to lead in their various aspects. The statement by Mrs Rega, the TIC, that they make use of members in the department to staff-develop others indicates that teachers are given opportunities to utilize their expertise for the benefit of other members. This signifies the existence of distributed leadership in the school.

The adage 'Two heads (or more) are better than one' by Cole (2004, p. 178) suggests that different people working on a task produce more credible results than a sole individual. In a similar lane, school heads need teachers for the successful implementation of the curriculum. Speaking about teachers and school heads working together at school, Chan et al. (2019) advocate that when school heads and teachers work together, the resultant effect is school improvement. Mrs Rega elaborated about leadership practices at her school by saying:

There are different committees here that are led by different teachers, which means the head shares some leadership activities with staff members. I lead the Infants Department as the TIC, and the deputy head supervises grades 3 to 5, so I can say, yes, she shares leadership activities with us.

She cited examples that depicted the stretching of leadership activities to staff members. She mentioned the different committees at the school, suggesting that the principal distribute leadership to other members.

Since Mrs Rega was the TIC, she doubled up as a class teacher and a supervisor for the Infants Department. She supervised teachers in her department, informed them of the level of their performance, and staff-developed them, thus displaying characteristics of instructional leadership. As the TIC, she provided us with the infants' staff development plans and held programmes, which indicated activities that teachers were staff developed in and those who facilitated the training workshops. Different teachers took part to deliver different topics as indicated by the documents analysed. She applauded the principal's enactment of distributed leadership in the school.

Case 2: The story of Mrs Ndaba

Mrs Ndaba is a vibrant, seasoned teacher who taught Grade 7 at

Bepura Primary School. At the time of study, she was slightly over 50 years old and held a bachelor's degree in education and a master's degree, both with a specialty in music. She had experience of over 25 years teaching in different primary schools. In addition to teaching, she also chaired the Discipline and Entertainment committees at the school.

Concerning the school vision, Mrs Ndaba explained how it was created:

We have a vision and mission statement from the Ministry and as a school, we also came up with our own vision and mission statements, separate from those of the Ministry. ... We asked ourselves how we were going to attain the Ministry vision and mission as Bepura Primary School, so we formulated our own vision, mission, and objectives.

Mrs Ndaba explained that the school's vision statement was crafted out of the generic Ministry vision. The aim was to achieve the needs of the school and at the same time achieve the Ministry vision from which the school vision was crafted. The quote 'we came up with our own vision' suggests participation by many in the exercise, thereby portraying distributed leadership. She further clarified who was involved in the crafting of the school-specific vision:

The vision and mission statements were crafted by everyone, because I remember when we started crafting them, everyone was involved. However, there was a task force to guide people to keep on focusing on the vision of the Ministry, so that we stand guided. So, there was a committee that worked with teachers and parents to come up with our vision and mission.

The quote suggests an important instructional leadership strategy employed by the principal of involving teachers in crafting the school-specific vision. Mrs Ndaba talked of every member being involved, thus suggesting a broad base of ideas that the task force could choose from to come up with a solid vision for the school. The creation of a task force by the principal enabled a few members to harness all the ideas from the broad base and come up with a concrete vision for the school. An analysis of the documents on the formulation of the school vision brought to our attention by Mrs Ndaba had information which suggested a shared activity. A collaborative practice took place in this activity, hence conforming to Spillane's (2005) assertion that school heads cannot lead schools to greatness as lone individuals; they need the participation of other members.

Mrs Ndaba's response on who supervised teachers at their school indicated that the school principal distributed leadership to other members at the school. She said:

The school head, deputy head, and the TIC are the main supervisors here. My supervisor, who is the school head, visits each teacher twice a term for those he supervises, grades 6 and 7. The other grades are supervised by the deputy head and the TIC.

Mrs Ndaba reported that the principal also observed teachers in class teaching. When we analyzed the narrative reports, which were a form of feedback to teachers, written by the school principal, we discovered that they were detailed. The act of observing lessons, writing reports, and giving feedback to teachers signified the principal's involvement in instructional supervisory activities. The sharing of grades to supervise with the deputy head and the TIC suggests distributed leadership.

Beverborg et al. (2015) advocated that staff-developing teachers

helps improve their instructional practice and ultimately learner performance. Staff-development activities took place at Bepura Primary School, as evidenced by Mrs Ndaba's response:

Normally, once or twice a term, we have some workshops in the school. At times, we are given the honor to come up with some topics for workshops from what we would have observed from our teaching and say this needs staff development.

The quote indicates that staff-development activities took place at Bepura Primary School. The involvement of teachers in coming up with topics for staff development clearly indicates an important distributed leadership practice in the school.

Spillane (2009) stated that staff members play central roles in the workday of the school head, as they take some responsibility for some activities done at the school, thus indicating shared accountability of instructional activities at the school. Concerning her views about the school head's interest in distributing leadership, Mrs Ndaba commended the school head's leadership practice by saying:

I do not think he holds everything to himself. He normally uses committees. There are committees that comprise the deputy head, the TIC, the head, and other senior teachers in the school.

Mrs Ndaba's comment indicates that the school head shared leadership activities with teachers. This was done in the form of committees that were in place to cater to different tasks in the school. This practice suggests the enactment of distributed leadership. The school head worked along with teachers in the school, thereby tapping into and making great use of the expertise of teachers for the improvement of academic performance at the school.

Case 3: The Story of Mr Nyika

At the time of study, Mr Nyika was a seasoned 60-year-old teacher whose teaching experience spanned over 30 years. He holds a Certificate in Education in primary school teaching and a Bachelor of Education degree in Education Management. He was the senior teacher at Chrim Primary School during the time of our visit. He had been at the school for the previous seven years and taught different grades during his stay. During the time of our visit, he was teaching Grade 5. He was the second oldest and most experienced teacher at the school, after the school head.

Allen et al. (2018) explained that '*vision statements focus on the destination - where the school aims to go - whereas mission statements focus on the journey how the school moves forward to reach that vision*'. This implies that, in schools, members need to know where their school intends to go and how they will get there. For this to happen, teachers are supposed to understand the school's vision. Since school vision is a fundamental element in the improvement of schools (Murphy & Torre, 2015) we were interested to know how the vision of the school was formed. Mr Nyika responded by saying:

The responsible authority created the vision of the school, which every teacher abides by. Teachers play an important role in implementing objectives as set by the school authority so that the vision and mission are attained.

Chrim Primary School is a private school, and a board of directors, which included the founder of the school, formulated the vision and mission of the school. The task of the teachers was to work towards meeting the objectives that were set by the responsible authority. Although teachers were not involved in creating the vision of the

school because of it being a private school, Mr Nyika's explanation points out that the board of directors, which comprised more than one person, formulated the vision. Gunawan (2017) advocated that school heads refer to the school's vision and mission when developing a work program for the school and when directing school activities. This understanding, coupled with Mr Nyika's statements, indicates that teacher activities were bound by the school's vision and mission statements.

Aunga and Masare (2017) encouraged regular classroom visits by instructional leaders to have direct experience of how work is done in classrooms and to understand classroom undertakings. Through this practice, school heads can appropriately guide their teachers. We asked Mr Nyika how supervision of teachers was done at the school, to which he responded as follows:

Mostly, it is the head who conducts lesson observations. Here and there, the deputy head and TIC also visit classes. Our school is a small one such that the deputy head and the TIC have classes to teach, so the head wants them to concentrate more on their classes than lesson observations; that is why he does most of the class visits.

Even though the principal did most of the lesson observations, distributed leadership practices were noted in the sense that the deputy head and the TIC also observed lessons, though on a limited scale, because they also had classes to attend to.

On the question of how feedback was provided to teachers by the head, Mr Nyika said:

The feedback comes in different ways. There is immediate feedback just after the lesson, highlighting areas not done well and those done through a written report. The narrative report is usually given after two days.

Feedback is an important instructional activity performed by the principal. The act of writing narrative reports and suggesting ways to improve performance indicated that the principal was a leader who carried out his instructional leadership roles. Martin (2018) emphasized the giving of timely feedback as an important instructional leadership practice that provided teachers with curriculum direction.

In finding out about staff-development programmes, Mr Nyika agreed that the school held staff-development activities. He pointed this out when he said:

The school has programmes for staff development. Normally, we hold three staff-development activities per term. Also, if there are training programmes at the District Office, some teachers attend and when they come back, the staff-develop others.

Mr Nyika's statement indicates the existence of the staff-development practice at the school. The indication of the frequency of when they are held and how teachers give feedback to others after having attended outside-the-school workshops indicates that staff development is practiced at the school. When we analysed staff development record books and records of meetings, we noted that different staff development activities were planned for and held. In the meetings record book, deliberations on staff development activities were noted and these tallied with what was recorded in the staff development record books. The analysed documents indicated that there was teacher participation in building up staff development activities at Chrim Primary School. This, in addition to the submission of topics for staff development, suggests a distributed leadership practice at the school.

Discussion and Findings of the Study

The school vision provides treasured information about the purpose of a school's existence. It serves as an unspoken contract between the school and its stakeholders to strengthen their jointly agreed purpose. The three cases in this study indicated that their schools had school-specific visions whose generation was determined by the different contexts of the schools. Mrs Rega and Mrs Ndaba indicated that they had participated in the formulation of their school-specific visions. This was a result of the distributed leadership practice in the school. An analysis of documents at two schools, Matanga and Bepura indicated that teachers participated while working as teams to come up with draft school visions, which were later consolidated into the school vision statement by a smaller group that was led by the school head. A difference occurred at Chrim Primary School, however, where the school vision was formulated by the responsible authority and the teachers' duty was high performance to meet the set vision. The vision and mission for the school were generated with the help of board members, hence displaying shared responsibility, which could have been emulated by the principal, leading him to enact distributed leadership practices at the school. The involvement of different members in the formulation of the school visions suggests how school heads enacted distributed leadership. The school heads' understanding of the importance of distributed leadership is evident in their avoiding the one man knows all syndrome.

The school heads observed lessons and provided teachers with feedback on their performance. As instructional leaders, the school heads redefined their roles to be prime learners striving for quality in education (Manaseh, 2016). They worked with teachers in managing the curriculum and, in addition, helped build up strengths and reduce the weaknesses in their teachers through supervision and feedback activities. The three school heads supervised their teachers and gave them feedback, thus playing their role of instructional leadership. They also made use of other senior members to supervise teachers' classroom activities, thereby enacting distributed leadership. Lesson observation crits that were analysed in the schools indicated the involvement of other members in the supervisory activity. *This supervision matrix indicated the school heads' strategy in enacting distributed leadership.*

Yasser et al. (2015) advocated that school performance improves when school heads create positive working conditions in their schools. Harris et al. (2017) and Pentang (2022) believed that it is a show of dynamism when instructional leaders support the professional development of teachers at their schools. This was evident at the three schools, where staff development was a common practice and both teacher and principal-driven. All the participants indicated that there were staff-development programmes in the three schools, which were quite effective in enhancing teachers' instructional performance. Mrs Rega was given the green light by her principal to develop other teachers in the Infants Department with or without the presence of the principal, thus indicating authority being delegated to other members by the principal. The distributed leadership practice was also enacted at Bepura Primary School, where teachers were sometimes allowed to come up with some topics for workshops from their day-to-day operations. The same applied at Chrim Primary School, as indicated by Mr Nyika, who explained that teachers were sometimes asked to contribute topics for staff development. Salo et al. (2015) emphasized that

effective school heads organize professional development activities to improve the knowledge acquisition of their teachers. Thus, the implementation of staff development in the three schools was an important leadership practice enacted by the school heads.

Dimmock (2012) believed that distributed leadership is capacity-building, in that extending leadership to school members has the potential of increasing the capacity of schools. In line with this, it can be said that school heads and distributed leadership are leadership-capacity builders. Building the leadership capacity of teachers entailed developing teachers' ability to lead different school tasks. While capacity-building took place in different ways, depending on school context, a common observation among the schools was their principal's commitment to building the leadership capacity of their staff members by affording them opportunities to lead different committees. Staff development plans and staff development records that were analysed in the schools complemented the data on staff development that was given by the respondents; there was an indication of staff involvement in coming up with topics for staff development. This investment of time and effort by school heads in developing the capacities of teachers suggests a benefit in the future (Huggins et al., 2017). Day and Sammons (2013) suggested that capacity-building teachers is a way of sustaining school improvement.

Conclusion

School heads are the first in command on the school organogram in public schools. This is different in private schools, where the founder or board of directors has the final say. Despite this, the instructional leadership practices of school heads determine the performance of schools, as they work with teachers and learners daily. This study concludes that in the schools that participated, school heads enacted distributed leadership practices. This very well sounded to have been the reason behind the high academic performance in the participating schools. A collaborative function existed in the schools, as evidenced by committees in all the schools, where teachers took leadership responsibilities.

Instructional leadership practices underpin the instructional performance of teachers. We discovered that school heads improved instruction through visioning schools, lesson observations, giving feedback to teachers, and creating positive school environments. These instructional leadership activities were enacted in schools through the engagement of vice school heads, TICs, committees, and other members of staff with the appropriate knowledge and skills to lead, hence distributing leadership.

The study aimed at exploring how distributed leadership practices were enacted in high-performing Zimbabwean primary schools. Based on the research question and the findings, the study concludes that school heads enacted distributed leadership through engaging other staff members in the process of performing school work. Accountability and complexities in schools supposedly made school heads enact distributed leadership to achieve school goals. Leading a school as a solo individual is not in line with the dictates of distributed leadership. It made sense for school heads to distribute leadership through engaging multiple individuals (Hairon, 2017).

The researchers acknowledge the limitation of this research study caused by the small sample size, which was limited to one district, three high performing schools and three teachers. This inhibits the generalizability of the research findings to other districts. However,

the sample was selected based on purposive sampling, where the researchers were eager to gather data from knowledgeable participants with knowledge on how distributed leadership practice was enacted in high performing primary schools. These findings can, however, be generalised to highly performing schools in the district and further research covering many districts and different schools can be conducted to be able to generalise over different school systems.

Recommendations

From the distributed leadership perspective, school heads cannot be the know-all in school leadership; it needs the involvement of other members. Sharing accountability with other members of staff contributes to improved school performance. There was shared responsibility in the three schools, hence their high performance. Nguyen et al. (2017) believed that the practice of sharing instructional leadership indicates active teamwork between school heads and teachers on curriculum and assessment matters. Hence, by enacting a distributed leadership practice in schools, there was improved instructional performance at the schools. Distributed leadership is the way to go in schools.

School heads carry out most of the community outreach activities, which involve sourcing resources and collaborating with council offices, school boards, and government offices. These activities take up much of the school heads' time, which they should use for instructional activities. It is therefore recommended that some of the workload be shared in schools to reduce pressure on school heads. In line with this, Nguyen et al. (2017) further stated that instructional leadership should not be confined to the principal alone but expanded to other members of the school, irrespective of them holding formal or informal leadership positions. The belief is that distributing leadership is a practical way of reducing the workload of school heads (Leithwood & Mascall, 2008).

For improved performance in schools, it is critical that the Ministry sensitizes school heads on the importance of enacting distributed leadership in schools. Such grounding on the importance of enacting distributed leadership practices in schools contributes to high learner academic performances and the Ministry must take upon itself to ensure that the distributed leadership practice is enacted in all schools irrespective of their resource base and underperformance. This might, in turn, increase the academic performance of different schools. A further study may be carried out involving a bigger number of teachers and school heads across schools in different districts of Zimbabwe using the base findings from this study. This might be an eye opener on the importance of the distributed leadership practice.

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